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IMPLEMENTING ICT WHEN TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION - A QUESTION OF SUPPORTING TEACHERS' MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to support teaching and learning practices at universities has become widely spread through digitalization strategies and to enhance efficiency. It brings new possibilities and challenges and a growing number of studies show how it affects students' learning and motivation [1]. In this paper we will look at how the implementation of ICT affects the conditions under which the teachers work and are motivated for creating motivating teaching. At Aalborg University (AAU), in a research project "Future directions of problem-based learning in a digital age", a subproject is studying how changes, when implementing new ICT, are affecting the pedagogical support of students' learning. The research group have documented the ICT implementation of a bigger change, and in this paper, student surveys and an interview with a teacher will be used to illuminate the challenges and the influences on motivation that teachers experience when trying to integrate courses and projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching in a Problem Based Learning (PBL) environment as done at Aalborg University (AAU) is for teachers to actively work with and have directions for the pedagogical approach used at the university. At AAU, the pedagogical PBL models cover a variety of problem

understandings from rather structured problems to ill-structured and very complex problems [2]. The PBL approach at the university is based on 9 guiding principles which are meant to support a mix of collaboration and project management skills as well as subject specific skills through an integrated structure of course work and project work [3].

A semester in general is structured with three 5 ECTS courses and a 15 ECTS project work. Application

Figur 1. Illustration of semester structure at AAU

of knowledge from the courses to the more in depth work in the large project is crucial for the whole structure of the curriculum. Integration of courses and project is therefore important [3]. Although the PBL-model is a distinctive feature of Aalborg University, the principles have been challenged in recent years. Lack of resources and a change of semester courses to be individual courses with related stand-alone exams has impacted the ability to integrate courses and projects [4]. Students' projects though, are still cornerstones in many curricula and the knowledge from courses still have to support and be included in the projects.

However, surveys have shown that both students and teachers have difficulties integrating knowledge from courses into the project work [5],[6]. Many teachers are aware of improving their teaching strategies and have been involved in different forms of new pedagogic approaches as flipped classroom, gaming, new ICT platforms etc.

Under the cross-faculty research project "Future directions of problem-based learning in a digital age" (PBL Future) [7], a subproject is studying how changing to an ICT supported teaching approach affect the learning conditions and the PBL support. In a co-creation process [8] between the research group, under the PBL Future project, and teachers at a 4th semester bachelor program in Media Technology, a new ICT based semester structure has been established and run for the first time in spring 2019 and again in spring 2020.

From running the three courses relatively separate and having a semester project running parallel, with a wide framework for students' choice of what to work with and how to integrate things from the courses, a new flipped and integrated semester project was developed. In this case of changing to an ICT supported teaching strategy the flipped learning approach has been used. We have seen that the flipped learning approach can be a great support for more active learning when doing in-class activities, as the flipped learning approach builds on some of the same learning theories as PBL, such as social and active learning theories [9],[10]. Research though show that teachers using the flipped learning approach have to put an extra effort into motivating the students, especially because the approach is relying on ICT based self-study materials that can be difficult for students to get through [11],[5].

Studies at Aalborg University shows that students are highly motivated when doing their project work, but the motivation can be lacking in course-work [6]. Looking at self-determination theory by Ryan and Deci [12], intrinsic motivation is dependent on three basic needs: autonomy, competence development and relatedness. Looking at the AAU PBL model the biggest emphasis on these three basic needs is found in students' project work, where they work in groups with self-defined problems and have time for in-depth studying what they themselves have chosen to engage in. They have autonomy of what to work with, and relatedness to the group, whom they do the project together with. In courses, the study plan is stricter and based on the disciplinary learning objectives of the course subject. This research project running at two full semesters is building on the theory, that integration between project work and coursework will increase the intrinsic motivation with students, as they will be able to draw on the motivation for the project when doing project related work in the courses. Designing the semester structure that support students' motivation while implementing ICT is the rationale behind the initiative done at 4th semester Media Technology. In this paper, we want to put focus on the teachers' motivation and ability to go through such huge changes in their teaching practice which leads to the general research question: What are the conditions for teachers' motivation when starting ICT based teaching in a PBL environment aiming at integrating courses and projects, and how is the pedagogical approach affected in this transition?

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

When teachers implement ICT into their teaching strategy the whole practice can be affected. Illeris [13] presents three basic dimensions for planning and analysing learning: *Content*, *Incentive* and *Interaction*. The teachers of 4th semester had to plan and practice their teaching according to the flipped and integrated semester concept and we will use Illeris' figure to analyse how these basic dimensions are changing and further we will look at how this change affects the teachers and their motivation. As teachers implement new ICT they have to *interact* with a new materiality. In this case teachers have to interact with video, sound, pictures and other flipped learning material, and they are to communicate and cooperate the *content* and *incentive* of their teaching within new digital interaction forms. Teachers have to get skilled within ICT to communicate and create the pedagogical aimed interaction cf. PBL at AAU. By looking into the planning and practice of the 4th semester concept we will be able to see an example of how the ICT implementation affects the basic dimensions of learning. Further we will, by looking at the

Figur 2. Illeris' three dimentionen af læring [13 p.118]

implementation of the new ICT based concept, from a teacher perspective, illuminate the effect of the implementation on the teacher's motivation.

Ryan and Deci and the self-determination theory are traditionally only looking at students' motivation, but in a new article 2020, they focus on the teachers' perspective of motivation [12]. Teachers also need motivational support to create motivational teaching for their students. Ryan & Deci indeed point out that the teachers' position today is filled with overwhelming demands from both above (administration and policies) and below (students and parents), which can make it difficult to be a motivating teacher. Teachers have, like their students, the same basic needs for *autonomy*, *competences* within the content of teaching and *relatedness*, all to support their self motivation, take initiative, be engaged and do adjustments in their teaching [12]. Studies show that motivated teachers make more motivated students [14]. We will bring this perspective of motivation theory into use while looking at the conditions in which teachers of the 4th semester is implementing new ICT while working on integration.

3. CASE STUDY: THE 4TH SEMESTER OF MEDIA TECHNOLOGY

4th semester Media Technology is an Engineering Education based on mathematics, technology and humanistic disciplines. Almost all teachers are educated within engineering and science, but are interested in the pedagogical aspects, especially because not all students have an interest or find themselves motivated in subjects as math or programming [15]. Five teachers are running the three courses listed as 5 ECTS each: Audio Processing (AP), Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE) and Physical Interface Design (PID), and the semester project is 15 ECTS with the theme Sound Computing and Sensor Technology [16]. All three courses have been flipped simultaneously from semester start in 2019. One of the courses had undergone the transition towards a flipped approach several years prior. According to the teacher, these years had included many mistakes and experiences, leading the course to its current format, including its didactic and pedagogical strategy. The AP course that we will look further into in this paper has one main course teacher who has not been working with the flipped learning approach before this project started. The AP course has not been well liked by the students.

4. METHODOLOGY CONSIDERATIONS

The authors of this paper were following the 'experiment' on the 4th semester, and collected data throughout the entire semesters from 2018 - 2020. Different kind of data has been collected, but in this paper focusing on the teachers' motivation only three forms of data will be used to illuminate the effect of ICT on teachers' motivation for changing teaching practice. A student survey from October 2019, evaluating the first run of the flipped and integrated semester concept, will be used to look at how the teachers were affected by the feedback and recommendations to change their teaching approach in spring 2020. These data give insight in the feedback that the teachers had to adjust their teaching according to. In this evaluating survey 2019, there were 59 students enrolled at the 4th semester. 40 out of the 59 students answered the survey and we will in this paper draw on some of the overall evaluation outcomes [17]. Further we will use data from semi-structured interviews [18] done in February 2020 with 4th semester teachers. The focus of the interviews was as follows: Experiences done in 2019 and the planning process of the 2020 semester, outline of the 2020 concept and how the research group have supported the development. Finally we have used observations from in-class sessions and the

learning platform Moodle. As many factors play a role when looking at the effect of implementing ICT in a teaching practice, we have chosen to look at only one of the courses as a case study for this paper [19] and thereby go deeper into the complexity of handling the transformation to the new flipped and integrated semester concept. The AP course were chosen and a one hour interview with the main teacher of the course has been fully transcribed and anonymized.

From the beginning of the process it was decided that the teachers and researchers would develop the new semester in cooperation. During the process our roles have shifted between co-creation, passive participation, active participation and complete participation [20]. The longitudinal studies meant that it has been an imperative to reflect the different data as well as give immediate feedback to the teachers. This feedback system has been of great interest and well-liked by the teachers, who are not used to much feedback on their work, but we are aware that it might also have served as an element of pressuring the teachers' work.

5. MOVEMENTS WITHIN THE LEARNING DIMENSIONS WHEN IMPLEMENTING ICT

In summer 2019, the first run of the flipped and integrated semester was done, and expectedly there was room for improvements. Student surveys evaluating the semester were very informative and in general, students' feedback gave a lot of good advice as well as concrete suggestions for changes [17]. Teachers were given the feedback and it outlined problems with especially the integration between courses and project work. Feedback from students showed that a lot of the course content was not applicable to the projects and one reason for that was that the ICT were not aligned and thereby could not 'talk together'. Therefore, the technological platforms used at AP had to be changed entirely for the spring 2020. The teacher explains:

"We changed the entire technical platform. And that didn't come just like out of the blue to do that. So, we spent a lot of time getting the knowledge, getting the first parts. So, I don't feel too shy to say that I used part of my summer holiday for that, but I think it pays off. So, it's investment to the future."
(Teacher A, 17.30)

The AP teacher had to be qualified within the new ICT that he now had to use and a lot of resources had to be put in, getting qualified and knowing how to interact with a new ICT. Further we see that these tasks did not end with the planning process. The teacher had to be very agile and find new technological solutions handling problems that arose on the way. The teacher had to, after semester start, move the entire platform to a cloud solution to make sure all students, independent of their user hardware, could participate in the lectures. Cross-cutting ICT became essential for integration and for relating in a similar way to the teaching content. Students also outlined other problems concerning the interaction with ICT and recommended extensive change. The AP teacher reflects on the feedback saying:

"One of the feedbacks [from the students] was, I still remember it, it's a good way of putting that [...] Having a third-party guy's videos, coding on the computer is not too relevant for us and not motivating us" (Teacher A, 36.04).

This third-party guy's video material affected the relatedness between student and teacher and affected the students' ability to be motivated. Teaching in a PBL environment requires a social and active learning approach and the relatedness between teacher and student is very important for the facilitation of PBL supported teaching. The AP teacher chose to change his entire teaching content to plan for a

better relation with the students and thereby a better possibility for motivation in the teaching practice.

Student evaluations from 2019 formed a range of pressure for improving teaching practice. Beside extensive changes in the teaching content and change in ICT to enhance better integration, the students' feedback also placed a pressure on the teachers' internal and administrative communication. Students asked for a substantial coordination effort, including how to align courses, semester projects and exams better. Constructing a tighter scope-limiting frame for the semester projects became necessary for creating integration points across the courses.

Communication and integration found its peace in some common touch points, e.g. joint supervision, midterm presentation and joint workshop week. The AP teacher describes the communication like this:

"We spend more time this year of coordinating the initial plans. But now I think we're executing that separately, with some kind of touch points about the joint supervision. And some touch points in the mutual events. And I think this is much better, because it kind of concentrates the collaboration time to specific points that you don't feel all the time, that you should coordinate." (Teacher A, 23.02).

Creating these touch points for when and how to work on integration was planned in advance, meaning that regular communication between the teachers could be less. The integration initiative is thereby focused on those touchpoints and less holistic. The AP teacher explains how he needs to create a focus in all of these new and changing ways of doing his teaching practice:

"So we can interleave the focus maybe, but I think nobody should expect that all the courses are learned well and the projects are integrated at the same time. So right now, I'm openly focusing on the course. I invested a lot in the course and other courses as well [not on Media Technology]. If we can share the [ICT] platform next year we can look at better project integration. So that is my personal working, but I don't give up so it's not that we don't do it." (Teacher A, 53.34)

Many things had to be changed on the AP teacher's course just to get the ICT working and find technology to make integration possible across courses and semester project. He has had to be very agile reacting on all of the student feedback and adjusting his teaching on the go, and he has now had to draw a line for how much to embrace. He don't give up on the integration, but have had to choose a focus and integration can be looked at again when some of the ICT related teaching concerns are more stabilized.

6. TEACHERS' MOTIVATION

Ryan and Deci's perspective on the teachers' basic needs can be relevant for looking at the effect of implementing new ICT into a teaching practice. As the teacher at the AP course implement the new ICT and is working on creating a more integrated structure across the full semester, a lot of feedback for improvements have affected the teacher. Because the research group have been involved, a lot more feedback than usual have been given to the teachers and huge changes have been made on the basis of this. The AP teacher has had to qualify within new ICT competences, and he has had to change the ICT platform to create better conditions for integration and relating to the students. The teacher's basic need of feeling competent and being related to the students has been challenged because of the ICT mediated interaction. Teachers are in general responsible for the courses they

are teaching, and they have the autonomy within this framework, but integration puts new demands upon the teachers' autonomy. They have been challenged to cooperate and adjust their course so it is aligned with the other courses and the semester project, this by again changing ICT platform to an ICT that is cross-cutting and planning the content to fit common touch points across the semester. What before was one or two teachers' own domain in a course where they had the full autonomy, is now affected by teachers from the whole semester. Further teachers' feeling of relatedness have expanded from only concerning the students to in much higher degree also concerning the other teachers at the semester. Disciplinary and interdisciplinary collaboration is needed, and studies show that the communication is getting more complex all the more interdisciplinary the task is [21]. Settling on some joint touch points is a way of framing the communication to a certain degree making it easier to handle, but also limiting the actual integration. If the teachers don't communicate regularly they don't have the ability to adjust in an agile manner to what is happening in the actual teaching practice. As many changes have been necessary, handling the planning of students' learning abilities, because of the implementation of new ICT, teachers might run to the wall of lacking motivation. A lot of initiatives have been done both concerning adjusting the teaching to the ICT and working on the integration, but the AP teacher must conclude that not all can be done at the same time. Handling integration tasks while also working with ICT supported teaching is challenging to the teachers and their motivation because it pressures the teachers on all basic needs for being motivated.

7. CONCLUSION

Implementing ICT in a PBL environment and also supporting an integrated curriculum has shown to imply a lot of pressure on the teachers to make big adjustments in the teaching design, and it has affected their motivation. We conclude in relation to the three motivational factors: Competence development, relatedness and autonomy.

Competence development during the process of implementing ICT and a new teaching practice has been challenging. It is not only the technical issues but also developing new materials as well as defining and testing a new teaching and learning design that fits students' developmental process.

Being related to students during a change, learning and teaching process is demanding as students have to be 'on the same page' meaning that teachers have to follow students' developments to be able to communicate with the students. The importance of establishing a good communication is essential.

The teachers' autonomy is challenging even. There is still freedom and responsibility for the single teacher, but they have to recognize the bigger picture of integrating courses and project work and this pressures the teachers' autonomy.

A lot of pedagogical tasks working with integration have been placed in a defined frame to reduce the complexity of cooperation and communication among the teachers, but this also decreases the level of integration across the full semester. The ICT might at first increase the need for confined and autonomous teaching practises as a reaction to all of the changes needed when implementing new ICT in a teaching practice, but the AP teacher still has the motivation to work on improving the integration when the ICT changes don't take up so much time. It shows important when working with implementing ICT, while also aiming for an integrated curriculum structure, to make room for the teachers' development and adjustment of the practice. Both to ensure that the teachers are not pressured too

much and loose motivation in the process, and to ensure room for adjusting the teaching design and thereby ensuring the quality of the teaching.

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